

Decision support systems (DSS): information technology in a changing world

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Traditionally, geographical distances between potential centers and users of information, such as IRRI and universities, have made the acquisition and delivery of information intermittent and inconsistent. The significance of this physical distance has dramatically decreased with the advent of the computer, and more recently, the Internet, which have become effective and efficient tools for delivering information both locally and globally. In the agricultural sector, which is in the midst of powerful changes influenced by industrialization and modernization, farm consolidations, reduced or eliminated subsidies, environmental limitations, land use conflicts, biotechnology, and increased overall risk, the availability, accessibility, and application of contemporary expert agricultural information is of high priority for farmers, technicians, and researchers. In response to these changes and demands for the most current information, numerous scientific and academic institutions have turned to computerized decision support systems (DSS) as a means of packaging biological, agricultural, and technical information to make the information more easily accessible and useful for various beneficiaries in a rapidly transforming and competitive world.

Our objective in writing this review is to (1) articulate a coherent definition of DSS including the features they generally contain, (2) provide examples in agricultural and related sectors, (3) establish reasons or factors for their slow or lack of uptake, and (4) finally suggest strategies for increasing user acceptance. This paper is the first in a series related to DSS. The next three articles, immediately following this review, highlight specific DSSs.

What is a DSS?

There are many definitions of DSS but they usually fall into one of two categories: narrow or broad. The narrow definition takes the view that a DSS is an interactive computer program that uses analytical methods and models to help decisionmakers formulate alternatives for large unstructured problems, analyze their impacts, and then select appropriate solutions for implementation (Watkins and McKinney 1995). The DSS will essentially solve or give options for solving a given problem. The decision process is structured in a hierarchical manner, the user inputs various parameters, and the DSS essentially evaluates the relative impact of doing x instead of y . The broader definition incorporates the above narrow definition but also includes other technologies that support decisionmaking such as knowledge or information discovery systems, database systems, and geographic information systems (GIS) (Power 1997).

This review favors the broader perspective and defines a DSS as comprising the following: (a) it is computer-based, (b) it is an information and/or technology transfer agent, (c) it contributes to option selection, and (d) it aids decisionmaking irrespective of whether the solution is generated by the system itself or independently deduced by the user from the information provided.

Within this broad definition, it is further useful to think of DSS in terms of their primary driving source of information. Bhargava and Power (2001) have suggested the following five broad categories:

1. Communications-driven DSS emphasizes communications, collaboration, and shared decisionmaking support. Examples are simple bulletin boards, threaded e-mails, audio conferencing, web conferencing, document sharing, electronic mail, computer-supported face-to-face-meeting software, and interactive video. It enables two or more people to communicate with each other, share information, and coordinate their activities. Communications-driven DSS is often categorized according to a time/location matrix, using the distinction between same time (synchronous) and different times (asynchronous), and that between same place (face-to-face) and different places (distributed).
2. Data-driven DSS emphasizes access to and manipulation of time-series data from an internal or external database source. Users can

access relevant data by simple query and retrieval tools for further synthesis and analysis: an example is weather-related databases.

3. Document-driven DSS integrates a variety of storage and processing technologies to provide users document retrieval and analysis: this may sometimes be found in libraries.
4. Knowledge-driven DSS is an expert or rule-based system where facts, rules, information, and procedures are organized into schemes that allow for more informed and effective decisionmaking. This is also sometimes referred to as the "expert" type of DSS.
5. Model-driven DSS emphasizes access to and manipulation of a model, for example, statistical, financial, optimization, simulation, and deterministic, stochastic, or logic modeling. Model-driven DSS generally requires input data from the end-user to aid in analyzing a situation. (See also Power 1999 and Watkins and McKinney 1995.)

Developers envision the ultimate DSS to be a compendium of several types of DSS (Fig. 1) to generate user-friendly, helpful, and resourceful recommendations.

However, developing a DSS as represented in Figure 1 is complex, requiring multicriteria analysis by a diverse group of knowledge experts and facilitated by the latest computer and/or web-based technologies. In addition, the software architecture involved in developing this type of DSS requires a long-term commitment of financial resources; a resource often limited in the nonprofit agricultural research sector. Currently, the most innovative DSS of this type originates in the industrial, financial,

Fig. 1. The ideal DSS development model.

Source: Power (2000).

and commercial business sectors or within large government agencies.

This mini review and subsequent articles highlight knowledge- and model-driven DSS, the most frequently encountered types in the agriculture sector.

Who uses DSS?

DSS exist for a wide range of applications including business and organizational management, health, water resources, environment, agriculture, and transport systems. Within these sectors, the DSS can be targeted for a wide range of categories of people, environments, or jobs. For example, in the agricultural field, DSS can be designed for use by agronomists, soil scientists, agricultural engineers, or entomologists specifically, or by agricultural scientists, researchers, extension agents, students, and/or farmers in general. DSS can be further targeted for a variety of environments or agricultural commodities—for temperate or tropical conditions, rainfed or irrigated environments, upland or lowland areas, watershed or field levels, fruits or grains, rice or wheat, and others. In addition, DSS are developed by both the commercial and nonprofit sectors.

Most agricultural DSS aim to help companies/organizations/people realize their strategic aim of securing a competitive advantage through timely decisionmaking. In Europe, numerous DSS exist to predict appropriate pesticide application times for various crops including potato. Of these, the most common are Negfry (Denmark),¹ Prophy (Netherlands),² Plant Plus (Netherlands),³ and Simphyt (Germany),⁴ which focus on reducing fungicide inputs (Dowley and Leonard 2000). These four late-blight advice systems have the advantage of being in direct competition with each other and, as a result, may truly be useful for farmers. Each developer competes with the others to deliver the most accurate, reliable, and useful blight prediction system. In fact, the four systems were compared during a field test, where one outperformed the others. The “winning” developer can and does use the results to gain market share (see <http://dacom.nl/pavtest.html>).

Most nonprofit agricultural DSS also aim to help users realize their competitive advantage or profitability through timely decisionmaking, with the general goal of increasing field production yields. DSS originating from nonprofit institutions,

in most cases, tend to be free of charge or have minimal fees.

Tables 1 and 2 show some agriculture-related DSS and their particulars. Table 1 is presented to highlight the availability of numerous DSS for a wide range of agricultural and/or environmental applications and Table 2 to highlight DSS specific for rice production. In addition, they are listed because of their ease of accessibility via the Internet. If a particular DSS in Table 1 or 2 is not viewable or downloadable through the Internet, a contact person’s email address is referenced within the table. These tables are by no means comprehensive.

The most notable aspect of the DSS listed in Tables 1 and 2 is that a majority of the developers of the DSS system are nonprofit and publicly funded institutions. The exception is the CABI Compendium. In addition, they all require a fairly high level of computer literacy and competency in the use of the English language and scientific terminology. Lastly, most of the DSS have advanced state-of-the-art hardware/software or Internet connection (i.e., bandwidth) requirements for operation.

The target audience and/or environment for the DSS in Table 1 tend to be quite broad and sometimes very loosely defined. And although the information accessible via these DSS is useful, especially for policymakers and researchers interested in forecasting/simulating/testing hypotheses, its applicability and accuracy for a specific geographical area may be unreliable and risky in real terms for agriculture’s ultimate end-users, the extension worker and the farmer.

The rice DSS in Table 2 differ from those in Table 1 in that their focus is on a narrower geographical area. With a narrower focus, the information is perhaps more applicable for the area targeted and less risky for farmers; however, the information is of little use if the environment within a geographical area remains highly variable. For example, the rice DSS for California (CALEX/Rice), south and midwest (DD50), and Riverine areas of Australia (MaNage) cover a fairly large and homogeneous growing environment. In comparison, the DSS for the tropics and Asia have a more difficult and challenging task as they must try and cover a highly heterogeneous agricultural environment. Due to Asia’s complex environment and a developer’s financial, time, and human resource constraints, in the short term, many of these DSS focus on a single rice-growing environment, i.e., irrigated systems.

¹Danish Institute of Agricultural Sciences. ²Opticorp. ³Dacom Automatisering BV & Systems, Inc. ⁴German Authority for Agriculture and Food.

Table 1. Some types of agricultural DSS currently in use or under development.

DSS	Target audience and environment	Developer and access information	DSS category	Description
CABI Compendium	Scientists, researchers, and extension staff; worldwide	Cabi International, UK; http://pest.cabweb.org/cpc/cpchp.htm	Database- and knowledge driven	Pest management for various crops
CROPWAT	Scientists and irrigation engineers; worldwide	Land and water development division of FAO; http://www.fao.org/ag/AGL/AGLW/cropwat.htm	Model- and database-driven	Irrigation management
DSSAT (Decision Support System for Agrotechnology Transfer)	Scientists and researchers; worldwide	International Consortium for Agricultural Systems Applications (ICASA) and Department of Biology and Agricultural Engineering, University of Georgia; http://www.icasanet.org/dssat/	Database-driven, model-driven (CERES, CROPGRO, and CROPSIM systems)	For various crops, analyzes and displays outcomes of simulated agronomic experiments
HOWWET	Researchers, extension agents, and growers; Australia	Queensland Department of Primary Industries and Queensland Department of Natural Resources; http://www.dnr.qld.gov.au/longpdk/ausrain/how.htm	Database-driven	Plant-water interactions
MAS (Multi-Agent System for Natural Resource Management)	Scientists, researchers, and extension workers; worldwide	Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement (CIRAD), France; http://cormas.cirad.fr/	Model-driven	Uses CORMAS programming software for simulations of various natural resource management outcomes
NuMass (Nutrient Management Support System)	Scientists and researchers; worldwide	Cornell University, North Carolina University, University of Hawaii, and Texas A&M University deanna_osmond@ncsu.edu	Model- and database-driven	Soil nutrient management for various crops including rice, maize, cassava, etc.
WEPP (Water Erosion Prediction Project)	Scientists, researchers, and extension workers; worldwide	National Soil Erosion Research Laboratory – USDA-ARS; http://topsoil.nserl.purdue.edu/nserlweb/weppmain/wepp.html	Model-driven	WEPP is a process-based, distributed parameter, continuous simulation, water erosion prediction model for use on a PC

For a DSS developer, deducing the target audience and environment is admittedly a critical and challenging task. Nevertheless, outstanding DSS tend to have a clear idea of the audience to whom the information is targeted. For a DSS user, being aware of the target audience and the environment for which the DSS is developed is also vital, as well as discerning information and/or recommendations that are reliable and applicable to one's particular environment.

Issues for agricultural DSS

There is some debate on the use or value of DSS as a vehicle to communicate research results to farmers, agricultural technicians, extension agents, field advisors, and researchers (Parker and Campion 1997, Smith and Webster 1986). The debate is applicable whether the DSS is for use in developed countries or in the still developing part of the world. In some sectors, "the DSS technology is considered to

have passed through the hype phase, where performance expectations outstripped the potential for delivery, and now might be considered to be maturing" (Parker and Campion 1997, Wong 1995). Nevertheless, a literature review of agriculture-related DSS innovations indicates a general realization that although there are many useful, scientifically valid models or knowledge-based tools currently available, a majority of these are underused. This may be partly due to the DSS's narrow target audience or environment. But the problem is most likely compounded by insufficient initial attention directed at delivery, including graphic user interface design, and development of an integrated knowledge system. Delivery, within the Asian context, incorporates the idea of getting the information to the user in the most practical, user-friendly, universally accepted, easily adaptable, reliable, and consistent format.

Table 2. Rice-based decision support systems currently in use or under development.

System	Target audience and environment	Developer and access information	DSS category	Description
CALEX/RICE	Researchers, extension workers, and growers; northern California	University of California, Davis http://www.ipm.ucdavis.edu/IPMPROJECT/soft&db.html-CALEX/RICE 1.1	Knowledge-driven	Irrigated rice, whole crop management
DD50 (Degree Day 50)	Researchers, extension workers, and growers; southern and midwestern USA	University of Arkansas, Missouri, and Mississippi, Louisiana State University via the university extension systems; http://www.deltaweather.msstate.edu/	Model- and database-driven	Irrigated rice, crop growth, and management prediction
MaNage Rice	Consultants, extension workers, and growers; Riverina, Murray Valley, Australia	NSW Agriculture and CSIRO Division of Plant Industry; http://www.pi.csiro.au/Brochures/FactSheets/Decision/Support/manage_rice.htm	Model- and database-driven	Nitrogen management for the Amaroos rice variety
NuDSS (Nutrient Decision Support System)	Scientists, researchers, and extension workers; irrigated rice, Asia	Soil and Water Sciences Division, IRRI; C.Witt@cgiar.org	Model- and database-driven	Integrated nutrient management
PRICE (Pesticide Residues in Irrigated Cereal Ecosystems)	Policymakers and extension workers; irrigated rice, tropics	University of Newcastle Upon Tyne, UK; Natural Resources International, Ltd., UK Richard.Wilkins@newcastle.ac.uk	Model- and database-driven	Risk simulation for herbicide use in tropical irrigated rice
RicelPM	Researchers, extension workers, and students; tropics, Asia	IRRI and Center for Pest Information and Technology Transfer, University of Queensland; http://www.irri.org/	Knowledge-driven	Integrated pest management
ThaiRice	Researchers and extension workers; northern Thailand	University of Changmai; http://mccweb.agri.cmu.ac.th/research/DSSARM/ThaiRice/framework.html	Thai graphic user interface, CERES model and spatial database-driven	Integrated rice management system
TropRice	Researchers, extension workers and some farmers; irrigated rice areas, Asia	International Programs Management Office (IPMO), IRRI; http://www.irri.org/	Knowledge-driven	Integrated rice management system

Most agricultural DSS are developed by research scientists and engineers working within highly specialized technical domains. These domain experts have little or no experience in cognitive and user interface delivery concepts. Although the scientist's areas of specialization lead to high levels of efficiency in concept and content development, the DSS developed tend to be (1) highly complex; (2) directed at only other scientists or researchers with similar mind-sets and not necessarily the agricultural end-user (i.e., field-level agricultural technicians, extension field agents, or farmers); (3) directed at problems isolated from other production factors (e.g., they may only focus on fertilization, pest management, crop production management, weed control, or land use management, etc.); and (4) lacking in cost-benefit analysis (Ostergard and Goodell 2000, Parker and Champion 1997, Carrascal et al 1995). The idea of "delivery" is typically lim-

ited to technical and computer science aspects, neglecting aesthetics, use of appropriate terminology, ease of use, cost-benefit analyses, and integrated thought processes.

In addition, many agricultural scientists contend that crop management decisions are intrinsically "unstructured decisions," and thus application considerations ought to be ignored. Power (2001) defines unstructured decisions as a type of decision situation that is complex and no standard solutions exist for resolving the situation per se. Some or all of the structural elements of the decision situation are undefined, ill-defined, or unknown. For example, goals may be poorly defined, alternatives may be incomplete or noncomparable, and choice criteria may be hard to measure or difficult to link to goals (Power 2001). Trying to configure this unstructured decision state of affairs for crop management is a demanding, challenging, time-consum-

ing, and possibly impossible task, especially without the use of high-powered hardware and artificial-intelligent-type software systems. However, there are general guidelines, based on years of experimentation, which are specifically appropriate and must be supplied whenever feasible.

In addition to the issues discussed earlier, Bell and Chung (2000) have identified multidimensional factors that limit communication and DSS adoption within Asia, including disproportionately large numbers of farmers relative to land ownership; farmer education and beliefs; language and cultural diversity; access to resources and credit; limited communication channels including mass media: radio, television, telephone, cell phones, and infrastructure; limited access to extension systems, consultants, and universities; underfunded and undertrained extension systems; and limited private sector development.

Therefore, although DSS continue to change rapidly and enormous innovation is occurring, several factors have to be built into DSS development from the start to ensure widespread usage. These factors include

1. A clear perception of "who" the end-user or target audience is
2. An awareness of the costs and benefits associated in developing the DSS for the long term
3. Simplicity for long-term sustainability (especially in the current Asian agricultural environment)
4. Formative evaluation and testing at every stage of development involving all stakeholders
5. A formal program to train users
6. A long-term support and consultation for users if feasible
7. Information that is accurate, clear, constructive, and cost effective for decisionmaking.

Strategies for increased use

The DSS developer perspective

Figure 2 is a simple representation and proposal for DSS development that may alleviate some of the problems inherent in their construction. Many of these strategies are not new and have been touched upon by scientists as lessons learned in developing decision support tools (Bell and Chung 2000). The comments specified in Table 3 in conjunction with Figure 2 may be useful for developers of rice-related DSS in Asia.

The majority of the lessons suggested by scientists are in reference to the content of the DSS. For example, if the DSS is model-based, then limit

Fig. 2. Proposed DSS development cycle. GUI = graphical user interface, ICT = information and communication technology.

the amount of input data from the user or provide sufficient default values, indicate cost-benefit, show relative advantage, indicate risk, and answer the right questions. This is practical and constructive advice. However, the delivery aspect must also be more strongly emphasized and be continuously at the forefront of the development process. User-centered design is essential; it can be simple to complex, but the developer must be cognizant of its target audience, use formative evaluation, and design iteratively.

The DSS user perspective

Although Figure 2 and Table 3 are directed at DSS developers, they contain terminology and concepts that DSS users may also find helpful in evaluation and assessment during the iterative DSS development process. For example, users generally must evaluate and review the following:

1. Content is reviewed for accuracy, breadth (i.e., range of knowledge or skills covered), depth (i.e., degree of complexity and detail), clarity (i.e., how well text is written), and appropriateness (i.e., content is appropriate to the level

Table 3. Lessons learned by IRRI scientists in developing decision support tools.

Researcher	Comments
Achim Dobermann and Christian Witt in reference to a model-driven DSS	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Keep the amount of input data required as small as possible. 2. Keep the system itself as flexible as possible, i.e., cater to missing data. 3. Give users reasonable default values (for their conditions) — users seem to be afraid to enter a “wrong” value. 4. Design a generic system that can give site-specific recommendations. The users do not appreciate a very general system—IRRI is interested in all of Asia, but the users are only interested in their specific regions. The more specific a system is for their conditions, the better. 5. For a generic system, quick indicators are needed to narrow the system to the one of interest to the user.
Reimund Roetter	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Revise and refine — iterations, present the DSS to users, and continue to refine based on their new ideas for improvement. 2. Involve users of the DSS as soon as possible, that is, from the beginning. 3. Satisfy the need for clearly defined, sound underlying concepts. 4. Practice good documentation. 5. Present prototype models to other experts from the early stages.
Mark Bell in reference to a knowledge-driven DSS	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Focus — do not try to solve all problems at once; choose your target very well (recommendation from Richard Plant). 2. Simplify, simplify, simplify — users will decide if a system is worth the bother of using based on the balance between ease of use, time required, and expected benefit. 3. At times, you will have to give generalized specific recommendations — do this, even though it is typically frowned upon.

Source: Bell and Chung (2000).

of knowledge, skills, and experience of the target audience);

2. Usability is reviewed for technical operation (e.g., the DSS CD-ROM is easy to install or easy to access online, other software or “plug-ins” are easy to access and install, the DSS runs smoothly without hanging up or crashing, speed is adequate, and printability of key information is easy) and hardware/software requirements.
3. Design and delivery is reviewed for clarity of directions and instructions, interface design consistency (e.g., icon locations, menu terms, screen layout), on-screen text readability (e.g., font size and styles), and ease of navigation (e.g., users can easily predict where a link will take them).

Clear and consistent terminology in assessment of DSS by users can be extremely useful for developers.

A strategic process for developing a DSS then includes the following types of individuals working as a team: (1) Domain expert—a person who has expertise in the domain or areas of interest in which a specific expert system is being developed; (2) Knowledge engineer—an information technology (IT) or artificial intelligence specialist responsible for the technical side of developing an expert system. (The domain expert, usually a scientist, works closely with a developer (i.e., the knowledge engineer) to capture the expert’s knowledge (especially rule and relationship information) in a computer-readable representation often called a knowledge base [Power 2001]); (3) Graphics designer—an individual who can develop the graphical user

interface (GUI)—a program interface that uses a computer’s graphics capabilities to make the program more pleasant and easier to use. Graphical interfaces use a pointing device to select objects, including icons, menus, text boxes, and other devices. A GUI includes standard formats for representing text and graphics (Power 2001); and (4) Monitoring and evaluation specialist—a neutral assessor to monitor, test, capture information, and summarize evaluation results during a DSS iterative development process.

Once a DSS is ready for release, the process is not concluded, especially within the socially, culturally, and economically complex Asian agricultural framework. In this context, a strategic aspect that receives scant attention is that of training and marketing of the DSS products to end-users. Within Asia’s culturally and educationally diverse agricultural sector, it cannot be assumed that end-users, whether they are scientists, managers, technicians, extension agents, NGOs, or farmers can access and manipulate the DSS. Many of the end-users must overcome their anxiety of new technology itself; however, once conquered, the access to information can be relatively painless and highly useful. Take for example, the head of a Municipal Agricultural Office, who participated in an information technology assessment workshop in the northern provinces of the Philippines. Although the agricultural officer was initially extremely hesitant and skeptical about approaching the computer, upon some brief instruction on TropRice, he was enthralled and eager to move around in the DSS using the mouse (without using the keypad). Thirty other extension agents attending this demonstration and evaluation activ-

ity, over a 2-day period, eventually conquered their anxiety, tried out TropRice, and gave feedback. An interesting note is that 90% of the extension agents had never worked on a personal computer, habitually delegating such work to their computer clerks.

The marketing of DSS does not have to be a cost-prohibitive activity. Many scientists and researchers travel regionally within Asia numerous times annually, conducting workshops, attending meetings and conferences, doing needs assessments, and other related activities. Many NARES, NGOs, universities, and individuals do have access to computers, if not yet the Internet. Showcasing the DSS to various counterparts regionally, and using CD-ROM or the Internet if feasible, would not be too difficult or demanding a task, especially when the information is practical and useful.

Conclusions

The Internet has indeed reduced the geographical distances between the target audiences and information sources—making information more easily accessible. At the same time, new developments in hardware and software technologies have encouraged the development of more user-friendly DSS that target a different level of the agricultural sector hierarchy. In the past, the problem has not been a lack of or existence of knowledge, but rather moving the knowledge from the research 'knowledge' centers to extension agents and farmers (Bell and Chung 2000). Although the extension systems charged with delivering information have all too often failed to meet their objectives in the past (Adhikarya 1994, Garforth and Lawrence 1999, Bell and Chung 2000), this failure may also be reflective of inconsistent delivery of information from the knowledge centers to the extension systems.

For research centers to have their findings reach farmers, new and more consistent forms of disseminating knowledge are essential for the future. DSS are a useful and legitimate means to deliver information as long as their development and production are done systematically, with adequate consideration given to target audience, target environment, target objective (i.e., what types of questions need to be answered), content complexity or simplicity, ease of navigation, and the graphical user interface, terminology, testing and evaluation, and an iterative plan. In addition, the DSS must be developed with sustainability and longevity as underpinning goals.

Within the complex environmental, cultural, and social context of Asia, the most useful agricultural DSS will most likely be those that simply

present expert information and allow the user to use his/her experiences in conjunction with information presented to garner solutions.

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